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Socio-Economic Suitability of AAC Block in Nepal

Anjay Kumar Mishra*, P. S. Aithal**

*Post Doctoral Research Scholar, Srinivas University, India and Associate Professor, Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy Nepal, Urlabari 3, Morang, Nepal

OrcidID: 0000-0003-2803-4918; Email: anjaymishra2000@gmail.com

**Professor, College of Management & Commerce, Srinivas University, Mangalore, India

OrcidID: 0000-0002-4691-8736; E-mail: psaithal@gmail.com

ABSTRACT:

The entire alternative given to society might not be accepted. Only technical parameters are not sufficient for distinguishing the acceptance or rejection of any alternative product to society. The Autoclaved Aerated Concrete Block (AAC) found technically suitable as alternative wall construction material. So, the aim of the paper is to analyze strength and weakness through acceptance and cost benefit of AAC Block at selected sites of construction in the Ward 10 and 11 of Bharatpur Metropolitan City of Nepal for the construction of residential buildings and hotels. To obtain the data, purposive sampling was used. The qualitative and quantitative data were taken to achieve the objectives of the research. Schedule survey and interview with key informant were applied for data collection. The study also presents various other comparisons based on the manufacturing process, spaces required and thermal insulation with regards to various literatures of both the present construction practices. After analysis of the collected data, recommendations are based on case studies. Use of AAC Block instead of Clay Bricks can save time and cost of buildings by 50% and 18% in single family units. So, AAC blocks are found acceptable and economic as alternative of bricks.

Keywords: acceptance, Comparison, construction, manufacture strength, weakness, Cost benefits etc.

Background

Most of the buildings recorded in Nepal have been constructed out of Clay bricks (Brick masonry). About 28.74% of the outer walls are constructed out of clay bricks bonded with cement whereas 41.38% are constructed with mud bonded clay bricks or stone in Nepal (Central Bureau of Statistics, 2011)[1]. However, the use of the clay bricks has increased over the last decades for the construction of buildings. Local people used the brick or stone masonry in mud mortar for the construction of residential buildings in the rural areas because of lack of other cementing material. The compressive strength of the AAC block was found to be 4.324 N/mm^2 even with a low density of 617.6 kg/m^3 when compared to a 3.402 N/mm^2 average compressive strength of brick of 1685.8 kg/m^3 density. However, the water absorption of the AAC block was found higher than that of the Clay brick (Khanal, Mishra and Ghimire, 2020)[2]. This properties conform AAC Block a suitable wall construction material though its acceptance of society also depends upon economic and cultural aspects.

Therefore, it has been recognized the need of the alternative of clay brick work. AAC block has been recognized as suitable material for building construction. Thus, a need of the study of the suitability of AAC block has been felt in the Bharatpur Metropolitan city for the construction of structures like hotels and residential buildings to analyze the acceptance.

Research Objectives

- The objective of this research is to analyse the acceptance and cost benefit of Autoclaved Aerated Concrete Block as Alternative Building Construction Material in the Bharatpur Metropolitan city for the construction of residential buildings and hotels.

Literature Review

Comparative Advantage of AAC Block

The need of housing has been estimated along with its challenges by Mishra and Sah(2018)[3]; Mishra, 2019[4]; Parajuli and Mishra 2020[5] and extensive review was conducted by Sah and Mishra 2018[6] followed by financial status resource mobilization for poor people by Mishra et al.(2020)[7] are sufficient to know need of searching alternative materials for house construction. AAC blocks are manufactured using natural raw materials such as clay, slate, shale, fly ash and volcanic materials. The manufacturing process doesn't include any fire which thus doesn't produce air pollution in the surrounding. They are known for their improved thermal properties along with its non-combustible and fire resisting nature (up to 1600 °C). The availability of AAC blocks in different custom sizes makes it economic for different sizes of walls. In addition to that, easy cutting, drilling, nailing, milling and grooving nature makes the block fulfill the individual requirement of the construction. Because of this, the reduction of operating cost of around 30% to 40% is observed in the AAC.

AAC blocks are 3-4 times lighter than the traditional bricks, which makes the construction work faster, easier and in turn makes use of less formworks and propping in construction. Additionally, the usage of these blocks reduces overall dead load of a building thereby allowing smaller cross-section of structural elements. Structurally in this construction, each wall and slab behave as a shear wall. These construction works are proven to be highly durable, low in maintenance and better colour (Desani, et al., 2016)[8].

Comparison between the AAC Block and Clay Brick

A comparison between AAC block and clay brick in respect of dimension, sound reduction index, thermal conductivity, energy saving, breakage & utilization, quality, efflorescence, fitting and chasing, contribution to carpet area and scale of maintenance is assessed to perceived uniform shape observation, better thermal insulation with energy saving up to 30%, saving of materials during construction, better quality of construction, better durability are some of the features in which AAC blocks are superior than clay brick(Desani, et al., 2016)[8].

Methodology

Study on AAC Block for the comparison with clay brick on building construction was done for the suitability of AAC Blocks in building construction. The study was conducted at different commercial buildings in the Bharatpur area. The figure 1; shows the design framework of study. The figure shows that the suitability of AAC Block depends upon the technical, social, and economical and environmental aspect. Based on our previous study technical suitability has been confirmed through lab work. So the business process and site application, society acceptance and economic suitability analyses through users, architects, and engineers, the questionnaire survey collected from the different level of personnel who are directly and indirectly related with design and implementation. Design data were collected from the designer as well as from IS standard, norms for the rate analysis to analyze and compare through data.

Fig: 1 Conceptual Framework

Study Area

For the research work, selected buildings that were being constructed in Bharatpur, which have used AAC Block were considered. In order to choose the sample among the population the Building approved from the Bharatpur Metropolitan City (BMC) were selected as BMC is the main agency for the approval of construction of buildings and construction materials.

Two buildings were selected purposively from overall BMC from approved list which were to use AAC blocks in the construction. Many buildings in BMC are concentrated in the city area because of the ease in administrative procedures and access for the construction. Thus, the study was based on the available information and data for the project, the personal interview and observation were carried out through the questionnaire survey with the key personnel.

Following buildings of table 1 were selected purposively taken as the sample for the study:

Table 1 List of Building Selected for Research

S.no	Building	Address	Metropolitan City	Remarks
1	Hotel Siraichuli	Bharatpur	Bharatpur	On going
2	Chitwan Garden Resort	Bharatpur	Bharatpur	On going

Data Collection Primary Data

Primary data are the main data for the analysis and interpretation of result for this research work.

➤ Dimensions Measurement

Standard provides a varied dimensions of the blocks 400 – 600 mm (length), 200 to 300 mm (height) and 100 – 250 mm of (width) as per IS 2385 part III (Bureau of Indian Standards, 1984) whereas NBC 119 400 [9]mm (length), 200mm(width) 100, 150 and 200 mm (Height) whereas the same block could have length of 200 mm (half brick)(Nepal Bureau of Standards and Metrology, 1985)[10].

Each masonry unit of clay brick as per National Building Code 109, the standard recommended dimensions of a clay brick is 240 (length), 115 (width) and 57 (height)(DUDBC,1994)[11].

Thus suitability of the AAC blocks is performed in the study after the measurements and data collection on the basis of compressive strength, dry density and water absorption test performed for 25 samples.

➤ **Materials Measurement**

For materials used in during construction for AAC blocks and red clay brick, an analysis is performed among 5 walls for two different sites. The analyzed heading for the materials are:

- i. Layer of mortar (Cumec) :
The volume of mortar required in the joints
- ii. Number of brick (Numbers)
The number of individual bricks or blocks required in the size of the wall
- iii. Time for specific wall (hrs)
The time required for completion of the specific size of the wall.
- iv. Joints of Bricks
The number of the joints in the walls
- v. Cost of mortar
The cost of the mortar used in the wall
- vi. Cost of labor
The cost of the labor depending upon the numbers of labor involved for the completion of the wall.
- vii. Shape of specific wall
- viii. Plastering
If there is the use of plastering for the final finish of the wall
- ix. Flexibility
What other purpose could the blocks be used as.
- x. Runner and Stiffness
The reinforcement used in the wall during the use of the particular block (either of clay brick or AAC block) wall.

Two bricks walls of 10' x 10' x 9" and one 10' x 8' x 8" and other 10' x 10' x 9" AAC block walls were used for the comparative analysis and is presented in the result and discussion portion of the report.

Site visit and assessment

Site visits were made to the construction sites to assess the actual implementation of the AAC blocks in site. In the site, the construction works were carried under the site supervisor for placing the AAC block systematically. Interview and discussions were made with the implementing team regarding the comparison between brick and AAC, time taken for placing the brick and AAC block on walls, debates about cost, and strength of AAC in comparison to brick

Key Informant Interview

Many interviews with the major stake holders, workers, site superiors, engineers, client, contractors, users, about the suitability of AAC block, its advantages& disadvantages of using AAC block as alternative building materials were held for the study. The interview worked as key information for the

research. The information regarding the construction, i.e, scalability, investment, space for curing, manufacturing capacity and workers requirement were collected during the survey.

Questionnaire survey

The questions were designed to analyze the knowledge, and barriers for adopting in context to traditional materials.

For the actual implementation of building materials in the field, site visits were made. To conclude the factors that hinder the implementation of AAC blocks in construction, questionnaire interviews were conducted with the Architects, Engineers and Users involved in decision making for the use of AAC block.

A total of 30 numbers of random samples were selected as the sample size for the unknown population size.

Use of Likert Scale in Ranking

Likert scale was developed in 1932 for measuring the attitudes where the respondents agrees or disagrees to the statement by a level. This is used to explain the strength or intensity of the statement with respect to different respondents where respondents are made to choose between different categories (McLeod, 2019)[12]. For the study, to find the rank of the different factors, three points scale was prepared as very high (Score 5), high (Score = 3) and low (Score = 1). Thus, with the numbers of respondents and provided score, a score is provided to the given factors and ranked likewise.

The score

$$\text{Score of the factor} = P_{\text{Very High}} \times 5 + P_{\text{High}} \times 3 + P_{\text{low}} * 1$$

$P_{\text{very high}}$ = Percentage of respondents on opinion on the factor with very high impact

P_{high} = Percentage of respondents on the opinion on the factor with high impact

P_{low} = Percentage of respondents on the opinion on the factor with low impact

Secondary Data

As for the secondary data, the unit rate of the products and the materials quantity required is taken from the “District rate of Chitwan” for the economic analysis in two sites. Based on different literatures the suitability of the AAC blocks over the use of clay bricks at the present context is done in the study. Literatures reviews, of building materials and other relevant journals were studied in this process, various publications on AAC Block were also reviewed.

Data Analysis

Comparative study of acceptance and cost effectiveness were done.

Research Matrix

The research can be summarized as research matrix in table 2.

Table 2; Research Matrix

S.no	Objective	Variables	Collection Methods	Analysis Methods
1	To access the comparative strength and weakness of AAC Block in comparison of red clay bricks	Size of equipment, Raw materials for manufacture, Space for curing, Manufacturing capacity, Investment, Scalability, Workers required	Based on Documents, observation, Key informant interview	Comparative analysis
		<u>During Construction</u> Layer of mortar, number of brick for specific wall size, Time for specific wall size, Joints for specification wall size, Cost of mortar, Cost of labor, Shape for specific wall, Plastering for specific wall, Flexibility for specific wall, Runners and stiffness for specific wall	At site, Based on selected specific wall, Comparative study will be done	Comparative analysis of cost effectiveness
2	To analyse the acceptance and cost benefit of AAC Block at selected sites of construction in the study area.	Environment Friendly, Light weight, Cost Saving, Energy Efficient, Easy Workability, Quality, Breakage, Soil Consumption, Green Product, Cost Estimate, Users view, AAC acceptance	Key informant interviews, Documents, Standards, Standard Norms, Contract, Questionnaire Survey	Comparative analysis, Cost Analysis

Comparative Analysis

The analysis of comparative strength and weakness of AAC Block in comparison of Clay bricks was carried during manufacturing and construction process.

Comparative Analysis of AAC Block during its Manufacturing with the Clay Brick

Manufacturing Process for AAC Block

AAC blocks fabricating measure begins with crude materials planning. Owsiak et al. (2015)[13] , and Rathi, O. & Khandve, P., (2015)[14] highlighted AAC Block as environmental friendly. Rundown of

crude materials and important subtleties are referenced underneath. Figure 2 shows the stream diagram of the creation of the AAC block.

Figure 2 Flow Chart Showing Manufacturing Process of AAC Block

AAC is produced using silica, fly debris/sand, lime, concrete, gypsum and water, to which a growing specialist is added. The AAC fabricating measure begins when the sand is ground to the necessary artfulness in a ball factory. Crude materials are then naturally gauged and estimated in the blender alongside water and aluminum glue. Coal fly debris is shipped off electronic scale in the grouping working by siphon at the base slurry tank to be estimated. At the point when the slurry focus shows up at the grouping prerequisite, the control framework will kill the siphon to stop siphon slurry. The deliberate slurry will be legitimately released into projecting blender. Lime and concrete will be shipped off electronic scale in the bunching working by single screw transport at the lower part of their storehouses.

When estimating shows up at the necessary quality, they will be shipped off projecting blender by screw transport. Aluminum powder will be estimated by manual, and added into aluminum blender to be readied suspending fluid individually for each form. The completed the process of suspending fluid can be straightforwardly added into the projecting blender. The slurry temperature ought to be shown up at required cycle temperature prior to projecting and shape the lower part of the projecting blender by ship vehicle. In the wake of blending, the slurry is filled metal molds in which growing operators responds with different components. The blending brings about a synthetic response that grows the combination to frame little, finely-scattered air spaces.

The molds are shipped off a pre-restoring space for a few hours. At that point the semi-strong materials are moved to the cutting machine. The cutting machine cuts the shaped square, utilizing steel wires, into the size needed for the structure components. The items homogeneity joined with the high exactness cutting innovation, brings about pieces with dimensional resiliences of 1/16". The cut AAC block in the necessary accuracy is then gathered before autoclave machine utilizing crane with the base plate. The last stage in the creation cycle is steam pressure restoring in autoclaves for as long as 12 hours kept up at pressure 1.2 MPa and at 185 °C temperature roughly. Square, boards and other AAC components are taken out from the autoclave, bundled and shipped off the completed item stockpiling. AAC strengthened components, for example, section boards, and lintels contain steel fortification work that is treated for erosion with water based acryline, and afterward positioned in the molds before the slurry is added. The assembling cycle is then equivalent to depict above for unreinforced components.

Manufacturing Process of Clay Brick

Clay bricks producing measure begins with crude materials planning. Rundown of crude materials and applicable subtleties are referenced beneath. Figure 3; is the flow chart showing the typical manufacturing process of clay brick.

Figure 3; Flow Chart Showing Manufacturing Process of Clay Brick

Blocks since the beginning of times have been produced using materials extricated from the top layer of surface. This material is by and large dirt. The properties of this mud are reliant on the geological attributes of the source and the profundity of extraction from the top layer of surface. Single dirt or various muds with various attributes can be combined with the block expansion of water to create a green mud base prepared for the block making measure. Additionally blocks by and large take attributes from the encompassing earth sources.

Sand (Silica), earth (Alumina), little extent of Lime, Iron Oxide and Magnesia is combined alongside the water in the blending plant. A long dirt segment or slug shape is made and afterward wire cut into singular block units. Completions can be smooth, on the other hand a surface surfaces can apply by the expansion of sand or finishing the face e.g., rusticated or drag confronted. The blocks made through this technique are ordinarily punctured and might be strong however without frogs. Or on the other hand blocks are framed by shape boxes. This cycle should either be possible by hand by skilled worker who produces each block in turn or programmed where huge number of blocks can be created at one time. Blocks utilizing these strategies are ordinarily caused frogs albeit some to can be strong. The formed block left for environmental drying of the surface. The following stage is pre-warming. It is to guarantee the block is totally dry. Furnaces are kept at temperature of 80 – 120 Celsius with high dampness. This permits the block to dry from the back to front and forestalls blasting.

The ovens temperatures are then expanded up to scope of 900-1200 Celsius. These temperatures are kept up all together for the dirt particles and pollutants to intertwine to deliver a hard-climate evidence material. The block oven is moved to the new area for the terminating of the following groups of creation. Air is then brought into furnace in a controlled way considering a controlled cooling environment for the blocks. This controlled cooling abstains from breaking and additionally mutilation of the blocks. Once cooled the blocks are dealt with for arranging/pressing and circulation. This drying/relieving measure for the most part can be taken as between 18-40 hours for standard shapes, and

significantly more for authority things. Earth blocks a structure material works in amicability with other structure materials and offers a wide scope of tones and shifting surface. It is a strong, perpetual and low upkeep material that gives enduring excellence and acknowledging esteem.

Other Comparison Regarding Manufacture

As based on the telephone conversations, Key Informant Survey, with the manufacturing team; the project managers, supervisor and the marketing managers, following responses regarding the AAC manufacturing is summed up.

A) Space for Curing

In AAC Block, the curing takes place on the main mixture only for a time period of 1.5 hours. The curing is the main part of the AAC Block which makes it light block used for building construction. Thus, it doesn't take a large area or doesn't require area separate for curing. Further, curing portion of the block is performed in the autoclave where the blocks are steamed where further gaining of strength is achieved in blocks.

In Clay bricks, drying/curing process generally can take between 18-40 hours for standard shapes, and even longer for specialist items. It requires larger area for drying before and cooling after the preparation in the brick kilns. This is done before the usage of the brick in construction. The curing process of AAC Block is done on the main mixture which doesn't require another larger area and whereas for clay bricks, the process of curing is done after manufacturing process in huge area.

This was observed and verified in the factory where it has large number of stocks of AAC Blocks and in the clay bricks curing process.

B) Manufacturing Capacity

While visiting a production factory of AAC Block in Malaykhu it was found that 147.84 cumec per days is the capacity of that plant with AAC Block. There is a team for that manufacture process of 39 to 48 numbers of workers working as a team for this plant per day for manufacturing of the given units of the production.

Clay bricks production mostly depends upon the working nature of the workers rather than the capacity of any machines of the kind of autoclaved machines.

The manufacturing capacity of AAC Block as team work, it can manufacture 147.84 cbm per days and more as that of clay brick are manufactured in high number depending on the number of workers. This was observed while the manufacturing process in respective

C) Investment

From the visit of the factory and their plant machinery and equipment certain inquiry were made about the investment of company. It has been said that around 40 crores of the investment was schedule there for the whole project of AAC Blocks. The factory area is around 5 *bigha* (approximately 3,64,500sqft) on the Malaykhu. The stock capacity is also well managed and the wastage is managed well in factory surrounding. The factory we visited was well managed in system for client and technical person for visit.

For the clay bricks production, it is said that the investment is about 9 to 10 crores of the whole project. For the manufacture, the production covers lots of area as of space near about 20 bighasor more. This huge area is covered because of its manufacturing process as well as the stocking capacity. The clay bricks are manufactured in a limited period, the clay bricks are not manufactured in rainy season and thus requirement of larger stocksfor the supply on the rainy season becomes essential.

The investment on AAC Block is around 35-40 core as of that clay brick has investment of around 9-10 core.

D) Scalability

The AAC Blocks are now replacing the bricks due its light weight, it is easily available, and many structured are constructed with the aac blocks, its demand are increasing day by day. The AAC block are easy to use with less wastage, show the workability and makes look the wall finishing good. The AAC is now growing in market and is starting to be consistent. The clay bricks are used in many residential buildings for the construction.

E) Worker’s Requirements

While AAC Block needs a team of around 39 – 48 workers in a team than Clay bricks manufacturing requires a big number of workers on the team.

Comparative Analysis of AAC Block during its Construction

Quantity analysis of the construction of the AAC block and Brick wall for the construction of square rooms of different sizes are shown in Table 3 and 4. The specific wall size of AAC is 10’ x 10’ x 8” from the building construction site of Hotel Siraichuli Block ‘A’ ‘Interior wall’

Table 3; Sample Wall of Hotel Siraichuli for AAC Block

Description	Units	Wall 1	Wall 2	Wall 3	Wall 4	Wall 5	Mean
Layer of mortar	Cumec	0.152	0.152	0.152	0.152	0.152	0.152
Number of AAC	Numbers	82	82	82	82	82	82
Time for specific wall	Hours	8	8	8	8	8	8
Joints of AAC	Numbers	246	246	246	246	246	246
Cost of mortar	NPR	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500
Cost of labor	NPR	6500	6500	6500	6500	6500	6500
Thickness of mortar	cm	1	1	1	1	1	1
Shape of specific wall		Square	Square	Square	Square	Square	Square
Plastering	Not Used						
Flexibility	Used as Lintel						
Runner and Stiffness	2 no of reinforcement of 8mm diameter						

The specific wall size of brick is 10' x 10' x 9" from the building construction site of hotel Siraichuli Block 'A' Basement part lift part & kitchen part

Table 4; Sample Wall of Hotel Siraichuli for Clay Brick

Description	Units	Wall 1	Wall 2	Wall 3	Wall 4	Wall 5	Mean
Layer of mortar	Cumec	0.57	0.57	0.57	0.57	0.57	0.57
Number of brick	Numbers	1226	1226	1226	1226	1226	1226
Time for specific wall	Hours	24	24	24	24	24	24
Joints of Bricks	Numbers	3678	3678	3678	3678	3678	3678
Cost of mortar	NPR	7500	7500	7500	7500	7500	7500
Cost of labor	NPR	5000	5000	5000	5000	5000	5000
Shape of specific wall		square	Square	square	square	square	square
Plastering	Used						
Flexibility	Used as Lintel						
Runner and Stiffness	3 no of reinforcement of 8mm diameter						

The specific wall size of AAC is 10' x 10' x 8" from the building construction site of Hotel Chitwan Garden 'Banquet Hall, Compound wall & kitchen part.

Table 5 Sample Wall of Chitwan Garden Resort for AAC Block

Description	Units	Wall 1	Wall 2	Wall 3	Wall 4	Wall 5	Mean
Layer of mortar	Cumec	0.14	0.15	0.14	0.13	0.14	0.14
Number of AAC	Numbers	73	68	73	78	73	73
Time for specific wall	Hours	6	6	6	6	6	6
Joints of AAC	Numbers	219	204	219	234	219	219
Cost of mortar	NPR	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500	4500
Cost of labor	NPR	6000	6000	6000	6000	6000	6000
Shape of specific wall	Square						
Plastering	Not Used						
Flexibility	Used as lintel						
Runner and Stiffness	2 no of reinforcement of 8mm diameter						

The specific wall size of brick is 10' x 10' x 9" from the building construction site of Hotel Chitwan Garden 'A' Banquet Hall, Compound wall & kitchen part

Table 6 Sample Wall of Chitwan Garden Resort for Clay Brick

Description	Units	Wall 1	Wall 2	Wall 3	Wall 4	Wall 5	Mean
Layer of mortar	Cumec	0.57	0.57	0.57	0.57	0.57	0.57
Number of brick	Numbers	1226	1226	1226	1226	1226	1226
Time for specific wall	Hours	24	24	24	24	24	24
Joints of Bricks	Numbers	3840	3810	3850	3846	3850	3840
Cost of mortar	NPR	7500	7500	7500	7500	7500	7500
Cost of labor	NPR	5000	5000	5000	5000	5000	5000
Shape of specific wall	Square						
Plastering	Used						
Flexibility	Used as Lintel						
Runner and Stiffness	2 no of reinforcement of 8mm diameter						

By analyzing the Table 3,4, 5 and 6, it was found that the mortar required for brick wall was found much higher compared to the AAC Block work. Similarly, the time required for completion of brick work is 3 to 4 fold higher compared to the time required for the completion of AAC Block work. Joints in the clay brick work are about 14 - 17 fold higher compared to block which makes the structure weak. Hence, the construction of AAC block is cheaper and faster compared to Clay Brick work. Along with that, in respect of quantity of the mortar and no need of plastering in AAC block construction, makes the construction more economical and feasible as the construction material.

Acceptance of AAC Blocks.

Awareness and Knowledge of the Stakeholders

The general question addressed to the stakeholders to evaluate the knowledge of the stakeholders on AAC Block were as follows

1. Do you have knowledge about AAC Block implication and application available in market?
2. Do you consider Autoclaved aerated blocks while design process?
3. How often you compare the AAC Block to replace the traditional mean of clay bricks available?

The Table 7 refers to the existing knowledge of the stakeholders and practice of different stakeholders regarding the AAC Blocks. Less than twenty five (<25) indicates that the stakeholders have no confidences regarding the subject at all. Less than fifty (<50) in that table represented that stakeholders have only partial confidence regarding the subject. Less than seventy five (<75) in the table represents

that the stake holders have confidence on the subject but have not implemented the topic on the regular basis. Equivalent to hundred (100) indicates that the stakeholders have sufficient knowledge regarding the subject to practice.

Analysis of structured questionnaire showed that most of the designers and engineers had better knowledge about AAC Block than the other group of respondents.

The finding regarding the present scenario knowledge regarding the AAC Blocks is obtained and shown in Table 7.

Table 7 Frequency of Awareness and Knowledge of Different Stakeholders Regarding AAC Block

S. N	Description	Architect (n=11)				Engineers (n=11)				Users (n=8)			
		<25	<50	<75	100	<25	<50	<75	100	<25	<50	<75	100
1	Knowledge of implication and application	0	0	5	6	3	0	4	4	5	2	1	0
2	Consideration of AAC Block	0	3	3	5	0	4	7	0	6	0	2	0
3	Comparison between AAC Blocks and Clay bricks	0	4	2	5	3	3	1	4	6	0	2	0

<25 = no confidence regarding the subject.

<50 = have only partial confidence.

<75 = have confidence but not implemented yet.

100 = have sufficient confident knowledge and have practiced.

Table 7 shows that any 8 out of 11 architects and engineers were found knowledgeable about AAC blocks, whereas about 56% of architects and only 4% of engineers were found knowledgeable about application of AAC. Similarly, 5 architects and 6 engineers think to consider AAC as alternate to brick over all users are found mostly unaware about the AAC blocks. Major number of architect respondent consider AAC block in design whereas most of the users do not consider AAC block in the design. Thus, users have to be made aware about the AAC block use in the design. Most of the designers, 5 numbers, compare about AAC blocks with clay bricks for its consideration in the use of construction, whereas the number is satisfactory among engineer and near to none for users who usually don't compare the AAC blocks with Clay brick for construction purpose.

Awareness of AAC Block

Figure 0; Showing the Awareness of AAC Blocks

Figure 4; shows about 70% of the respondents were found aware of AAC blockw whereas 7% are not sure about the AAC block.

Level of Knowledge of AAC Block

Figure 5; Level of Knowledge of AAC Block

Figure 5; shows that, 10% respondent said that, level of knowledge is excellent about AAC block whereas 30% said they have good knowledge, 23% said level of knowledge is moderate and 35% said they have low and very poor knowledge about AAC blocks.

Factors that Determines the Use of AAC Block in Construction Industry

Stakeholders Role on Selecting Building Materials

Figure 6 Stakeholders to Select the AAC Block

Figure 6; shows the analysis of the question concerning their roles in selecting the building materials during design and construction phase indicated that 60% architects, 23% engineers and 17% user's played role while selecting AAC Block.

Factors that Determine the Use of AAC Block

The questionnaire results for the question "What are the factors that determine the use of AAC Block?" was ranked based on three scale (Likert Scale) with respective scores for Very Critical (Score = 5), Critical (Score = 3) and Less Critical (Score = 1) and the following result was observed.

As shown in the table 8, labor availability is considered as the main factor that would determine the use of AAC block in construction. Another important factor is public perception about AAC block for the use of AAC block in construction.

Table 8 Rank of Factors that Determine the Use of AAC Block

What are the following factors that determine the use of AAC Blocks?	Very Critical	Critical	Less Critical	Score	Rank
Availability of materials in the market	7	13	7	1.456	8
Poor clients interest	14	13	0	2.753	3
Inadequate supply of the materials	11	12	4	2.185	5
Lack of labor	22	4	1	4.123	1
Non compatibility with other materials	7	19	1	1.531	7
Public perception	19	8	0	3.617	2
Doubtful durability and life span	10	16	1	2.049	6
Poor social acceptability by public	14	8	5	2.691	4
Non-commercial status	6	11	10	1.246	9

However, availability of materials in the market and non-commercial status of the AAC block is considered as least important factors for the use. Other than that, poor clients interest, poor social acceptability by public, inadequate supply of the materials, doubtful durability and life span and non-compatibility with other materials are given ranks of 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7 respectively. There is negligible breakage almost 100% utilization is possible with High strength without wastage in AAC block. It is Fire resistant. An AAC block has Superior sound absorption quality due to porous structure of block. An AAC block is Pest and moisture resistant (CARE, 2015)[15]. These properties were appreciated by Informant for promoting the use.

Barriers on Adopting AAC Block in Construction

Based on the questionnaire survey and Likert scale analysis on three scale very high (Score = 5), High (Score = 3) and Low (Score = 1), the barriers for adopting AAC blocks were ranked where rank 4 was received by two barriers as shown in the Table 10. Lack of standards was sought as the major barriers by the respondents whereas lack of government support/incentives were sought least important barriers for adopting AAC block in construction. Lack of competent labor, attitude of stakeholders towards AAC, inadequate knowledge, results of tests of the AAC blocks and low profit margins were ranked simultaneously as 2, 3, 4, 4 and 5 respectively. So, importance has to be given to producing of required standards in Nepal and creating competent labor than waiting for the government incentives and support for the adoption of the AAC blocks in construction here in Bharatpur.

Table 9; Rank of the Barriers on Adopting AAC Block in Construction

What are the barriers you feel for not adopting the use of AAC Blocks in our construction?	Very High	High	Low	Score	Rank
Inadequate Knowledge	10	10	0	2.667	4
More has to be done on the testing of the AAC Blocks	10	10	0	2.667	4
Low Profit Margin	4	11	5	1.183	5
Attitude of stakeholders towards these materials	15	6	1	3.500	3
Lack of standards	15	5	0	3.833	1
Level of competent labor	16	6	0	3.727	2
Lack of government support/incentives	2	9	9	0.649	6

To understand the belief of the respondents on the benefits to the construction industry in Nepal on adopting AAC blocks with respect to cost and time effectiveness, major portion of respondents, 36% of respondents were not sure of the benefits. Whereas, only 7% strongly agreed on the cost and time effectiveness of the AAC blocks in the construction industries. 32% agreed on its time and cost effectiveness. Whereas, 18% (Strongly Disagree) and 7% (Disagree), i.e., 25% of respondents disagree about the cost and time effectiveness of AAC blocks. Major respondent i.e., 32%, agreed on the statement. From the survey, it can be inferred that respondent were not sure of the benefits and cost effectiveness. The result of the survey is shown in the Figure 7.

Figure 7 Percentage of Respondent Responding on their Belief on Cost and Time Effectiveness of AAC Block

While interview with the person involved in building construction aspect adopting the AAC Blocks in building construction 53% of the respondents put their view on adopting AAC Block in building construction where 47% of respondent said no for adopting AAC Blocks in building construction.

The Factors Hindered for Selecting AAC Block

Figure 8 Factor Hindered for Selecting AAC Block

According to chart showed in Figure 8 it shows that above 50% lack of technical understanding of AAC is major factors that hinders for selecting AAC whereas lack expressed from client are also other factors that hindered for selecting AAC Blocks.

Cost Benefit Analysis

The financial status of low cost housing of Nepal has been earlier studied by Mishra et.al (2020)[6] reveals the better truth of here can be refereed. The calculation for the cost of the building for different size of the walls is done for AAC blocks and for “if replaced with bricks” with the rates taken from the Chitwan District Rate Analysis of Bharatpur Metropolitan City, 2076 and the deal with the supplier and the Hotel Siraichuli Pvt. Ltd. The standards regarding the AAC blocks couldn’t be found and hence reference of the deals with the supplier is taken to estimate the cost of the buildings which is followed by the estimate of the cost of the buildings if replaced with bricks.

The cost of the brick work is found to be less than the AAC blocks because of the monopoly market of AAC while considering only the work on walls. However, there is the saving in plaster amount which is in fact the savings for the AAC as discussed above in section 4.2.3 of this chapter. A total cost, as shown in the Table 10, seems to be less for AAC block wall than the Brick wall and a cost saving of 18% is observed. Thus, a financial benefit of 18% could be obtained on a work in a building while replacing brick wall by AAC block wall.

Table 10; Cost - Benefit Analysis

Description	AAC Block Wall	Brick Wall	Cost Saving
Cost of Wall Work with Mortar	9,133,120.08	8,905,175.08	18%
Plastering	817,338.30	2,878,673.90	
Total Cost	9,950,458.38	11,783,848.98	

Working note

❖ Calculation of materials for brick work

- Take a wall 10’X10’X9’’

Here,

$$\text{Volume of brick work} = 10 \times 10 \times 0.75 = 75 \text{ cuft} = 2.12 \text{ Cum}$$

$$\text{Size of brick} = 23 \times 11 \times 5 \text{ cm}$$

$$\text{Thickness of Mortar} = 1 \text{ cm}$$

$$\text{No. of brick} = \text{Volume of brick} / \text{Volume of 1 brick with Mortar}$$

Now,

$$\text{Volume of 1 brick with mortar} = 0.24 \times 0.12 \times 0.06 = 0.001728 \text{ cum}$$

$$\text{No. of brick} = 2.12 / 0.01265 = 1226 \text{ no's}$$

$$\text{Volume of brick's} = 0.23 \times 0.11 \times 0.06 \times 1226 = 1.54836 \text{ cum}$$

$$\text{Quantity of mortar} = 2.12 - 1.54836 = 0.57164 \text{ cum}$$

$$\text{Dry volume of mortar} = 0.57164 \times 1.33 = 0.76 \text{ cum}$$

$$\text{Quantity of cement} = 0.76 \times 1/7 \times 1440 = 156.4 \text{ kg} = 3.12 \text{ bags}$$

$$\text{Quantity of sand} = 0.76 \times 6/7 = 0.651 \text{ cum}$$

- Number of mortar joints = $3 \times 1226 = 3678 \text{ no's}$

❖ Calculation of materials for AAC block

- Take a wall 10’X10’X8’’

Here,

$$\text{Volume of AAC work} = 10 \times 10 \times 0.75 = 75 \text{ cuft} = 2.12 \text{ Cum}$$

Size of AAC block = 600 X 200 X 200 mm

Thickness of mortar = 1cm

No. of AAC block = volume of AAC block / Volume of 1 block with mortar

Now,

Volume of 1 brick with mortar = $0.61 \times 0.21 \times 0.21$
= 0.026 cum

No. of block = $2.12 / 0.026 = 81.53 = 82$ no's

Volume of block = $0.6 \times 0.2 \times 0.2 \times 82 = 1.968$ cum

Quantity of mortar = $2.12 - 1.968 = 0.152$ cum

Dry volume of mortar = $0.152 \times 1.33 = 0.20$ cum

Quantity of cement = $0.20 \times 1/7 \times 1440 = 41.14$ kg = 0.82 bags

Quantity of sand = $0.20 \times 6/7 = 0.17$ cum

➤ Number of mortar joints = $3 \times 82 = 246$ no's

Quantity of ACC Block used in Hotel Siraichuli Building Project

- 8'' thick external wall = 249.89 cum (As per Siraichuli Projects Quantity)
Area of the external wall = 13239 sq.ft
- 4'' thick internal wall = 311.38 cum (As per Siraichuli Projects Quantity)
Area of the external wall = 32993sq.ft
- Number of 8'' AAC block = 9995 no's
- Number of 4'' ACC block = 24910 no's
- Rate of sqft of work done (As per the deal between client and the supplier)
= 297.35 per sqft for 8''
= 157.5 per sqft for 4''

Total cost Nrs = $13239 \times 297.35 + 32993 \times 157.5$
= Nrs 9,133,120.08

If Brick is used

- 9'' thick external wall = 283.97 cum
- 4'' thick internal wall = 311.38 cum
- Number of 9'' brick = 159023 no's
- Number of 4'' brick = 174372 no's
- Cost of 9'' thick wall = 283.97×14722 (Chitwan District Rate)
= Nrs. 4,180,606.34
- Cost of 4'' thick wall = 311.38×15173 (Chitwan District Rate)
= Nrs. 4,724,568.74

Total cost in brick Nrs = Nrs. (4,180,606.34 + 4,724,568.74) = Nrs 8,905,175.08

Plaster work in brick.

Area of External wall for plaster work = 1234.65 sqm

Area of Internal wall for plaster work = 3,113.8sqm

Plaster work in external wall = 2×1234.65 (On both sides) = 2469.3 sqm

Plaster work in internal wall = 2×3113.8 (On both sides) = 6,227.6sqm

Rate of plaster work in external wall = 2469.3×331 (Chitwan District Rate)
= NPR.817, 338.3(Plastering works of 1:6 Cement sand)

Rate of plaster work in internal wall = $6,227.6 \times 331$ (Chitwan District Rate)
= NPR2,061,335.6 (Plastering works of 1:6 Cement sand)

Total amount of plaster work in wall = $817,338.3 + 2,061,335.6$
= NPR, 2,878,673.9

Plaster work in AAC Block

Area of External wall for plaster work = 1234.65 sqm

Now, Consideration of plastering on only outer part of external walls

Rate of plaster work in external wall = 2469.3 * 331 (Chitwan District Rate)

= NPR.817, 338.3 (Plastering works of 1:6 Cement sand)

CONCLUSIONS

AAC are found more environmental friendly as it uses the wastage fly ash as raw material. It was also found less labor intensive and lighter than clay bricks. The mortar required for brick wall was found much higher compared to the AAC Block work. The time required for completion of brick work is 3 to 4 fold higher compared to the time required for the completion of AAC Block work. Joints in the clay brick work are about 14 - 17 fold higher compared to block which makes the structure weak. Hence, the construction of AAC block is cheaper and faster compared to Clay Brick work. Along with that, in respect of quantity of the mortar and no need of plastering in AAC block construction, makes the construction more economical and feasible as the construction material AAC block constructions were found 15-20% (18% in average) economical compared to clay bricks.

However, knowledge about AAC block as construction material was found limited as engineers and construction contractors were found unaware about the use of AAC as alternative construction material. Clients requiring light weight construction material were found using AAC and the use trend is increasing in residential buildings too. But the use of AAC still has shown poor social acceptability, client interest and lack of technical understanding. These factors are hindering the AAC acceptability

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my deepest thanks to all the helping hands without which this work would not have been completed. This research is dedicated to all the people affected from COVID 19 and hope the world is going to come over this problem.

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